

Evaluation of heat protection and thermal physiological comfort of protective clothing fabrics for firefighters

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404517

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Introduction

Protective clothing for firefighters against heat and flame prevents the wearer from health risks or even life-threatening heat stress in extreme environmental conditions. However, the better the performance of the protective clothing, the less the heat generated from the human body is dissipated. The firefighter is not able to maintain body core temperature within normothermia and suffers from heat stress [1]. The components of personal protective equipment for firefighters include helmet, eye protection and goggles, hood, coat, trousers, gloves, and footwear. The construction and design of fire service protective turnout consist of three layers, the outer shell, vapor/moisture barrier, and thermal barrier [2]. The purpose of the outer shell is to provide flame resistance and protection from cuts and abrasions. The general used materials are Nomex/Kevlar blend (incorporating the heat resistance and tear resistance), Oxidized Pan fiber, PBI, aluminized PBI, etc. In this study, the sweating Torso was used to evaluate the thermal and evaporative properties of personal protection clothing (PPC) materials for the prediction of thermal physiological comfort [3,4,5,6]. The water-vapour permeability index, i_{mt} , was introduced to compare the effect with different fabric samples as an alternative way on evaluating PPC physiology [7].

Methods

Seven types of fabric assembly consisting of outer shell, moisture barrier, and thermal barrier were investigated by both of heat protection factors, flame and radiation (EN ISO 9151, EN ISO 6942: 2002 B), and physiological comfort factors, thermal resistance (R_{ct}), water vapour resistance (R_{et}), water-vapour permeability index (i_{mt}) (EN ISO 11092: 2014), and Torso measurements (ISO 18640-1). The statistical correlation analysis and ANOVA are used for factors and variance of samples analysis.

Table 1. Materials

Items/Samples	PPC-1	PPC-2	PPC-3	PPC-4	PPC-5	PPC-6	PPC-7
Outer shell	PBI x PBI-Para aramid	FR Meta aramid-Para aramid	Nomex Meta aramid-Para aramid	Nomex Meta aramid-Para aramid	Nomex Meta aramid-Para aramid	PRE PAN-OX fiber + Aramid	Aramid + Anti-static fiber
Moisture barrier	Aramid nonwoven + bi component ePTFE membrane	Aramid nonwoven + PU membrane	Aramid nonwoven + bi component ePTFE membrane	Aramid nonwoven + PTFE FR membrane	Aramid nonwoven + PTFE FR membrane	Aramid nonwoven + PTFE FR membrane	Aramid nonwoven + PTFE FR membrane
Thermal barrier	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Viscose lining	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Viscose lining	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Viscose lining	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Viscose lining	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Viscose lining	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Modacrylic lining	Aramid nonwoven + Aramid / FR Modacrylic lining
Weight (g/sqm)	595	547	561	561	559	616	527
Thickness (mm)	0.268	0.222	0.218	0.185	0.186	0.243	0.185

Results and discussion

With regard to two most important protection properties of firefighter's garment expressed by heat transfer-flame (HTI) and heat transfer-radiation (RHTI), all seven samples show satisfactory results either reaching level 1 or level 2, which complies with requirement of EN 469:2005. The test results may imply that the protection properties of firefighter's garment can be achieved by using these commercially available combinations of layered fabrics, regardless of the outer shell materials being PBI, Meta-aramid, Para-aramid, or Oxidized fiber. However, it was found that the PPC-1 of PBI outer shell exhibits the best performance in the heat protection, and PPC-2 and -3 rank the 2nd group, whereas the rest of samples are in the 3rd group.

The comfort properties of R_{et} and i_{mt} can be seen in Table 2 that the results of R_{et} for all seven samples have reached level 1 or level 2, lower than 30, which meets the requirement of EN 469:2005. The best values of R_{et} are PPC-3, PPC-1, PPC-7 and PPC-6 in order. Furthermore, the best values of i_{mt} are PPC-1 and PPC -3, while the worst ones are PPC-4 and PPC-5. The mean skin temperatures of Sweating Torso during the

protocol of 3 phases are shown in Figure 1 and some factors which reveal high correlation with each other are listed in Table 2 also. The results indicate that all the samples seem to have “cooling delay” and cooling effect during the activity phase, while PPC-3 and PPC-7 are among the best of PPCs. However, PPC-1 and PPC-2 show the two highest uncomfortable skin temperatures at the end of activity. The lowest condensed water uptake is PPC-6, and the highest ones are PPC-2 and PPC-1 accordingly.

Table 2. Test results of heat protection and comfort factors

Items/Samples	PPC-1	PPC-2	PPC-3	PPC-4	PPC-5	PPC-6	PPC-7
EN ISO 9151:1995							
HTI24	14.0(Level 2)	13.2(Level 2)	13.2(Level 2)	12.5(Level 1)	12.7(Level 1)	13.6(Level 2)	12.0(Level 1)
HTI24-HTI12	3.7(Level 1)	4.0(Level 2)	3.8(Level 1)	3.6(Level 1)	3.7(Level 1)	3.6(Level 1)	3.5(Level 1)
EN ISO 6942: 2002 B							
RHTI24	19.1(Level 2)	14.1(Level 1)	15.4(Level 1)	15.9(Level 1)	17.4(Level 1)	14(Level 1)	13.1(Level 1)
RHTI24-RHTI12	6.3(Level 2)	3.6(Level 1)	4.5(Level 2)	5.3(Level 2)	5.9(Level 2)	3.8(Level 1)	4.5(Level 2)
EN ISO 11092: 2014							
$R_{ct}(m^2K/W)$	0.143	0.110	0.126	0.094	0.101	0.127	0.095
$R_{et}(m^2 \times Pa/W)$	20.19(Level 2)	23.21(Level 2)	19.00(Level 2)	27.95(Level 2)	29.77(Level 2)	22.18(Level 2)	20.61(Level 2)
$i_{mt}(60XR_{ct}/R_{et})$	0.428	0.288	0.401	0.204	0.206	0.348	0.278
ISO 18640-1							
$R_{ct} * 10^{-3}(m^2K/W)$	92.4	78.7	77.6	71.6	68.2	91.8	69.5
Cooling delay, CD (min)	2.7	3.3	3.0	4.0	4.3	3.0	3.7
Sustained cooling, SC (°C/hr)	-1.09	-0.61	-0.75	-0.60	-0.43	-1.01	-0.43
Water uptake, (g)	38.0	40.4	36.5	36.7	36.0	31.2	36.8

Figure 1. Skin temperature of Torso (ISO 18640-1)

Conclusions

In this study, three indices, R_{ct} , CD (Cooling Delay), and SC (Sustained Cooling) seem to demonstrate a high degree of correlation in terms of standards EN SO 11092 and ISO 18640-1, but they are influenced critically by fabric weight and thickness. The R_{ct} , a heat protection factor, is an ambiguous one in protective clothing, while R_{et} does play a key part in this aspect. The i_{mt} , the ratio of R_{ct} over R_{et} , may mislead the performance due to the effect of thickness of firefighter jackets. For example, PPC-1 has the best heat protection properties but the highest skin temperature at the end of activity due to the highest weight and thickness leading to the higher

R_{ct} and i_{mt} . On the other hand, PPC-7 is the lightest and thinnest one, and presents good R_{et} value and the best cooling efficiency especially the sustained cooling ability. This reveals the R_{et} is more critical than i_{mt} for choosing a thick material as firefighter garments. Therefore, the better firefighter’s outfit should consider properly light-weighted and permeable in addition to having a satisfied heat protection.

References

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